

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF OFFICIAL DOCUMENTS

Bobojonov Baxtiyorjon Bahromjon o'g'li

Annotation: The factors mentioned make up the standard of documents' writing. Special forms help to focus readers' attention on major information and simplify process of making a deal.

Key words: Clarity, Precision, Formality, Accuracy, Structure, Appendices, Tone, performative, peculiarities.

Uzbekistan is a country located in Central Asia with a population of over 35 million people. Uzbekistan has a high demand for English language education as the country is rapidly developing and becoming more globalized. Teaching English in Uzbekistan can be an exciting and rewarding experience for those who are passionate about language education.

Why Teach English in Uzbekistan?

Uzbekistan is a unique destination for teaching English as it offers diverse cultural experiences, stunning landscapes, and friendly locals. The country has a rich history and culture, which can be explored through its ancient cities, bazaars, Islamic architecture, and traditional cuisine.

The demand for English language education in Uzbekistan is on the rise due to the increasing globalization of business and travel. The government of Uzbekistan has made significant efforts to promote English language proficiency among its citizens by implementing various programs and initiatives.

Teaching Opportunities in Uzbekistan

There are several opportunities for teaching English in Uzbekistan. The most common options include teaching at international schools, private language

institutes, universities, or as an independent freelancer.

International Schools: International schools offer excellent salaries and benefits packages that include housing allowances, health insurance, and transportation. These schools follow international curriculums such as the IB or Cambridge IGCSE. The students are usually from affluent families who speak multiple languages.

Private Language Institutes: Private language institutes offer flexible schedules and competitive salaries to teachers who have experience teaching ESL/EFL. Teachers can expect to teach children or adults from beginner to advanced levels.

Universities: Universities in Uzbekistan hire native English speakers as guest lecturers or full-time faculty members. These positions require a master's degree or higher in TESOL/TEFL or related fields.

Freelance Teaching: Freelance teaching allows teachers to work independently with flexible schedules. Freelance teachers can offer one-on-one classes or group classes at their homes or at students' homes.

Requirements for Teaching English in Uzbekistan

The requirements for teaching English in Uzbekistan vary depending on the employer. However, most employers require a bachelor's degree and a TEFL/TESOL certification. Some employers may also require previous teaching experience and knowledge of the Uzbek or Russian language.

Visa Requirements

Foreigners who wish to teach English in Uzbekistan must obtain a work visa before entering the country. The employer must provide the necessary documents for the visa application, including an invitation letter, employment contract, and passport copy.

Salary and Benefits

Salaries for teaching English in Uzbekistan vary depending on the employer,

qualifications, and experience. However, most teachers can expect to earn between \$800-\$2,000 USD per month. International schools and universities offer higher salaries and benefits packages that include housing allowances, health insurance, and transportation.

Living Costs

The cost of living in Uzbekistan is relatively low compared to other countries in the region. Rent for a one-bedroom apartment can range from \$150-\$500 USD per month depending on the location. Daily expenses such as food, transportation, and utilities are also affordable.

Teaching English in Uzbekistan can be an exciting opportunity for those who are passionate about language education. The country offers diverse cultural experiences, friendly locals, competitive salaries, and low living costs. With the increasing demand for English language education in Uzbekistan, there are plenty of opportunities available for qualified teachers.

The actuality of the course paper. Nowadays due to the development of international official partnership the interpreters are faced with the necessity of translating official papers from English into Russian because English is considered to be the language of world official relationships. In comparison with literary texts the texts of official documents are highly standardized: it concerns both the structure of the whole text and the arrangement of special paragraphs.

The analysis of researches is devoted to the linguistic peculiarities of official papers. And it shows that theory of writing official documents, on the one hand, reflects highly subjective approaches. On the other hand, such approaches are not unified in accordance with existing rules of formal English. Such influence really exists, but there are no accepted criteria for changes that should be taken into consideration. Thus, the main problems of people who write official papers are: how should they write it to sound correctly in the foreign language? How formal should they be in the content of documents, if even English-speaking people meet

difficulties drawing a line between formal and informal English

The language of documents is characterized by specific terms and expressions and also by those grammatical and syntactical patterns where translation can cause some difficulties. That is why we should know sufficient knowledge of grammatical, stylistic and lexical peculiarities of official papers to translate them correctly.

The aim of the course paper. Its subject comprises investigation of linguistic peculiarities of official papers and the specific character of translation.

The theoretical basis for the investigation is founded on the researches of well-known linguists: Arnold, Galperin, Gordon.

The Purpose of the research is to analyze peculiarities in texts of official documents, problems of their translation. It is performed through comprehension, interpretation and analysis of essential clauses.

The tasks of the research are:

to point out main features of formal English as the language of official papers;

to describe the peculiarities of official papers' translation.

to expose stylistic, grammatical and lexical peculiarities of official papers.

In order to solve these tasks have been used the methods of studying and analysis of theoretical literature and practical manuals.

The practical value of the course paper. In fact, the linguistic peculiarities of the structure and function of contracts in the world of official have not been given a clear understanding of the subject. The main factors of the theoretical significance of the research is to state the connection between all types of official papers while describing and analyzing distinctive features of the content of documents.

The practical significance of the research is to underline the main rules of writing official documents for those who are concerned about drawing up the

official documents. It also can be interesting for people studying problems of functional usage of formal and informal styles in English. The results of the research can be taken into consideration by students who are involved in studying English and English stylistics. As well it can be used for special courses of official English for students of Linguistics, Official and Economics.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Andryushkin A.P. Business English: Business English. 3rd ed. - Moscow .: Dashkov & Co, 2005.p-97
2. Brieger N. Advanced English Contacts.-London: Oxford University Press, 2013.p-24
3. Burak A.L Translation and intercultural communication: Stage 1 level words. -Moscow, 2005.p-21
4. Concise Oxford Dictionary, Oxford University Press, 2009.p-98
5. Cowie A.P. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary:-Oxford University Press, 2012.p-33
6. Demidov A.K. Smirnov E.A. Russian commercial correspondence: (for English speakers). -Moscow: Russian language, 2009.p-88
7. Galperin L.R. Stylistics. -Moscow: Higher School Publishing House,2010.p-55
8. Geffner A.B. Business Letters: The Easy Way.- New York: Barton's, 2008.p-66
9. Izrailevich E.E. Textbook of commercial correspondence and documents in English. – Moscow:2007.p-34
10. Koltunova M.V. Language and business communication:Standards. Rhetoric. Etiquette. Tutorial. - Moscow: Flint, 2000.p-167
11. Komissarov V.N. The general theory of translation / VN Commissars. -

Moscow CheRo 2008.p-89

12. Koty G.A., Gyulmisarov V.R. Business writing in English. Samples with a Russian translation: (Practical Guide). - Moscow: 1 Federal Bookselling Company, 2005.p-159

13. Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners.- London, 2006.p-72

14. Miram G.E., Daineko V.V., Taranukha L.A., Grischenko M.V., Gon A.M. Basic Translation: A Course of Lectures on Translation Theory. -Kyiv, 20010.p-64

15. Skrebnev Y.M. Fundamentals of English style: Textbook for high schools. -Moscow: Astrel, AST, 2008 – p-76